

**Efficacy of letrozole combined human menopausal gonadotropin in
ovulation induction in patients with polycystic ovary syndrome: a
meta-analysis of randomized clinical trials:**

a PRISMA-compliant article

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Abstract

Background: Relevant randomised clinical trials (RCTs) were evaluated to determine the efficacy of letrozole (LE) in conjunction with low-dose intramuscular injection (i.m.) of human menopausal gonadotropin (HMG) for induction of ovulation in patients with polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS).

Methods: We conducted a systematic literature search using PubMed, Medline, ISI Web of Science, CBMdisc, and the Cochrane Library databases. The standardised mean differences (SMDs) with 95 percent confidence intervals were evaluated using a fixed-effects model (CIs). To estimate the effects of letrozole (LE) in combination with i.m. injection of human menopausal gonadotropin (HMG) for induct of ovulation in patients with polycystic ovary syndrome, we used subgroup analysis,

sensitivity analysis, and publication bias analysis.

Results: 5 pertinent RCTs were included from the 836 retrieved studies. The LE + HMG group ovulation cycle count was radically higher than that of LE group with SMD (95% CI) of -3.51 [- 3.95–3.07] and $P < 0.00001$ (fixed-effects model). According to the therapy duration subgroup analysis was also carried out (<6 months or ≥ 6 months). No momentous heterogeneity among these subgroups, according to the overall effect subgroups (fixed-effects model, SMD=-3.22, 95% CI=[- 4.08,-2.37], $I^2 = 0\%$ and $P=0.85$). The outcomes of the pooled analysis were not tainted by the deletion of any single study, according to sensitivity analysis.

Conclusions: The combination of LE and HMG intramuscular injection has shown to have adequate therapeutic benefits in induction of ovulation, a short treatment cycle, and a significant diagnostic rate of pregnancy, making it a potential treatment option for PCOS infertile patients. In addition, further large-scale RCTs are needed to assess the long-term effectiveness of letrozole (LE) in conjunction with i.m. injections of human menopausal gonadotropin (HMG) on induction of ovulation in polycystic ovarian syndrome patients.

Abbreviations: LE=letrozole, HMG=human menopausal gonadotropin, PCOS=polycystic ovary syndrome, SD=standard deviation, SMD=standard mean differences, CIs=confidence intervals, randomized clinical trials=RCTs.

Keywords: Letrozole, Human menopausal gonadotropin, Polycystic ovary syndrome, Ovulation induction, Efficacy, Meta-analysis.

1. Introduction

PCOS (polycystic ovarian syndrome) - A widespread endocrine and reproductive condition occurs in women. It has excessive androgen levels, prolonged anovulation, polycystic ovarian alterations, and frequently associated with insulin resistance and obesity. [1,2]. According to statistics, about 5% -10% of young women suffer from this disease [3]. PCOS is habitually allied with ovulation disorders, & accounts for 70%-80% in anovulatory infertility [4]. The incidence rate is second only to tubal infertility, accounting for second of the causes of infertility [5].

Because the pituitary gland in PCOS patients is more sensitive to gonadotropin releasing hormone (GnRH), it secretes an excessive amount of luteinizing hormone (LH), which encourages the ovarian stroma and theca cells to create an excessive amount of androgen [6]. Androgen can interfere with hypothalamus pituitary ovary axis. As a result, it is impossible to form the LH peak in the middle of menstruation, so anovulation occurs [7]. The key to treating infertility - people with polycystic ovarian syndrome is ovulation induction therapy [8]. Currently, the first-line medicines in ovulation induction in PCOS patients include clomiphene, aromatase inhibitors, or human menopausal gonadotropin [9-12].

For the management of PCOS women with CC-resistant anovulation, aromatase

inhibitors (AIs) like letrozole or anastrozole have been introduced [13]. Letrozole inhibited oestrogen synthesis in ovary, allowing the hypothalamic-pituitary axis to be free of estrogenic negative feedback [14]. HMG contains FSH and LH hormones, mainly through the supplement of patients with gonadotropin is not enough to promote follicular maturation, ovulation and luteal development, which is more commonly used in clinic [15,16]. There is yet to be a consensus on the effects of letrozole and HMG in the management of PCOS individuals who are defiant to clomiphene citrate.

Relevant randomised clinical trials (RCTs) were evaluated to determine the efficacy of letrozole (LE) in conjunction with intramuscular injection (low-dose) of HMG on induction of ovulation in patients with PCOS.

2. Materials & methods

2.1. Investigational approach

This study followed the guidelines laid forth in Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions [17], it was reported using Prisma Statement Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses Statement [18]. We looked for RCTs published within September 2020 in following electronic databases: CNKI, PubMed web of science, VIP, Medline, Cochrane Library, CBM disc, ISI Web of Science, & Wanfang database. There were no restrictions on the use of words. The following words were used in the search strategy:

("Letrozole") AND ("human menopausal gonadotropin") AND ("Polycystic ovary syndrome"))).

2.2. Inclusion & exclusion criteria

The following investigations met inclusion criteria: a) randomised controlled trials that assessed induction of ovulation polycystic ovarian syndrome patients receiving letrozole coupled with menopausal gonadotropin treatment; b) RCTs.

The following were the criteria for exclusion: a) Observational study; b) Animal research, c) research of other new drug intervention; d) The outcome indicators of literature application can not be extracted or calculated; e) The data were repeatedly published.

2.3. Extraction of data and quality evaluation

The study was screened by two researchers, & in harmony with the study criteria (inclusion, exclusion). When there was any objection to a certain research, the third researcher was consulted to finally determine the selected researches. Literature screening flowchart explored in Figure 1. Two researchers blindly collected the capital data (first author, year of publication, research method, research object, sample size, average age, and course of treatment) and outcome indicators (ovulation induction). The effectiveness of the included studies was assessed using the bias risk assessment tool from the Cochrane Handbook for systematic reviews of interventions

(version 5.1.0). Figure 2 depicts the findings of the quality evaluation.

2.4. Statistical analysis

For data analysis and statistics of all outcome indicators, the Cochrane Collaboration's Review Manager Software (RevMan, version 5.2) was used. According to the heterogeneity test results, the effect model was determined. $I^2 \geq 50\%$ indicates greater heterogeneity, & the random effect model (RE) was selected; $I^2 \leq 50\%$ indicates that the heterogeneity seems to be within the acceptable range, fixed effect model (FE) is selected. WMD was used to combine continuous variables with binary variables, and RR was used to combine binary variables with continuous variables. When $P < 0.05$ was used, it was assumed that the changes in each outcome index were significant. Subgroup analysis was done to determine the origin of heterogeneity, and sensitivity analysis has been used to see how individual studies affected the overall results.

2.5. Approval on ethical grounds

3. Since this study was indeed a meta-analysis, which is a type of secondary analysis, no ethical approval was required.

4. Results

3.1. Study selection flowchart:

During the first literature search, 858 studies were discovered. Figure 1 depicts flow diagram of study selection process. We removed 164 citations during the first

screening of titles and abstracts, and of the 132 papers to be retrieved in favor of full text examination, 127 items eliminated: 76 didn't disclose baseline LVEF and/or heart function outcomes, 18 did not match the inclusion criteria, and 33 could not extract or compute the literature's outcome markers. As a result, the meta-analysis comprised five randomised, double-blind, controlled studies [19-23].

3.2. Included study characteristics:

Tables 1 and 2 describe the features of the studies that were included. A total of 14841 participants were included in the five trials that were eligible for the meta-analysis. Three hundred and twenty-six of them were randomly assigned to take letrozole (LE) in conjunction with human menopausal gonadotropin (hMG). One study was conducted in Western country, and four studies were conducted in eastern country. Each patient groups mean age and SD provided by the five studies. The duration of therapy ranged from 6-24 weeks. Five RCT studies compared letrozole (LE) and human menopausal gonadotropin with only human menopausal gonadotropin in patients with polycystic ovary syndrome [19-23]. Figure 2 depicts the risk of bias in the meta-analysis' randomised trials. In the majority of the trials, randomization was done using computer-generated random list / a randomly created numerical prototype [19-23]. There was a minimal probability of inadequate outcome data & selective outcome reporting in the randomised trials to include in investigation. Five of the randomised trials in our analysis had a high risk of subject and personnel blinding, as well as

outcome assessment [19-23]. Furthermore, all randomised trials had an unknown risk of additional bias. Finally, the quality of these investigations ranged from moderate to excellent.

3.3. Pooled analysis

Ovulation induction was considerably enhanced in patients with polycystic ovarian syndrome in the experimental group (fixed-effects model, 95 percent CI=[-3.95, -3 .07]; Fig 3A.). Considering heterogeneity existence (I²=67% and P=0.02; Fig 3A), we underwent sensitivity analysis. We removal two studies [19,21] from the analysis, the results indicated that across s the studies no heterogeneity was pragmatic (I²=0 and P=0.82; Fig 3B), and It had no effect on our primary ovulation induction analyses. (fixed-effects model, SMD=-2.39, 95% CI=[-3.16, -1.62]; Fig 3B.).

3.4. Analysis of subgroup

The length of treatment (<6 months or ≥6 months) was used to divide the participants into subgroups. The general pattern of pooled impact did not differ significantly by possible sources of heterogeneity, such as therapy duration, in the subgroup analyses (Fig 4). No momentous heterogeneity among all these categories in the overall effect (fixed-effects model, SMD=-3.22, 95 percent CI=[4.08,-2.37], I² = 0 percent, and P=0.85).

3.4. Sensitivity Analysis and Publication bias

The outcomes of the pooled analysis were not tainted by the exclusion of any one study, according to sensitivity analysis (data not shown). We removed two studies [21,22], and the findings showed no heterogeneity throughout research ($I^2=0$ and $P=0.82$; Fig 3B), and it had no effect on our primary analyses for ovulation induction (fixed-effects model, $SMD=-2.39$, 95 percent $CI=[-3.16, -1.62]$; Fig 3B.). Pooled analysis' result viewed as having elevated degree of confidence. In addition, we created funnel plots to assess publication bias. There was no publication bias in the funnel plots (Fig 5) for ovulation induction.

4. Discussion

The total count of ovulation cycles in LE + HMG group substantially greater than LE group, with an SMD (95 percent CI) of -3.51 [$3.95-3.07$] and P 0.00001, according to the current meta-analysis (fixed-effects model). The total impact showed no remarkable heterogeneity among those categories (fixed-effects model, $SMD=-3.22$, 95 percent $CI=[4.08,-2.37]$, $I^2 = 0\%$, and $P=0.85$). The results of the pooled analysis were not tainted by the exclusion of any one study, according to sensitivity analysis.

In this meta-analysis five RCTs were incorporated, which were high quality article. In individuals with polycystic ovarian syndrome, the combined results demonstrated that letrozole plus human menopausal gonadotropin improved ovulation induction more significantly. There are currently few large-scale clinical studies of letrozole

with menopausal gonadotropin in induction of ovulation among PCOS patients, and outcome indications are lacking. As a result, more research is needed to thoroughly understand the mechanism of letrozole with menopausal gonadotropin in induction of ovulation among PCOS patients.

Letrozole drug belongs to the category of aromatase inhibitor. Its mechanism of action includes central ovulation mechanism and peripheral ovulation induction mechanism. The mechanism of central ovulation is that pituitary secretes more follicle hormone through negative feedback [24,25]. The mechanism of peripheral ovulation induction is to block the process of transforming androgen into estrogen, lessen the accumulation of androgen in ovary & the expression of (IGF) insulin growth factor, so as to improve the ovarian response to hormone and promote ovulation [26]. Furthermore, Letrozole can act on the female reproductive system endometrium & cervix, endometrium thickness was increased, improves environment of sperm passing through, and provide implantation conditions for fertilized eggs. After letrozole withdrawal, the mechanism will establish a normal negative feedback regulation mechanism, avoid multiple follicles developing and growing at the same time, and effectively reduce the ovarian stimulation [27,28]. HMG promotes follicular growth and estradiol secretion by binding to FSH receptor [29]. HMG combined with Le can increase the sensitivity of ovary to GN, reduce the dosage of GN, control the number of follicles, and effectively reduce ovarian hyper stimulation [30].

The current meta-analysis has the advantage of being the first thorough study of the effects of letrozole coupled with menopausal gonadotropin in induction of ovulation among PCOS patients. Furthermore, because the included RCTs are homogeneous, the findings are clearer than any one research. The cardioprotective benefit of letrozole coupled with menopausal gonadotropin in individuals with polycystic ovarian syndrome is explained by reasonable biological processes. Our data collecting procedure was as thorough as feasible. We found no evidence of heterogeneity or publication bias. This review should give solid data on the cardioprotective impact of letrozole with menopausal gonadotropin in induction of ovulation among PCOS patients based on these criteria.

The current meta-analysis contains significant flaws as well. The most significant restriction found to be examined only lesser studies. In this study only five studies were worked with, so we couldn't do a meta-regression analysis. As a result, we were unable to assess the impacts in their entirety. Furthermore, since the result of this analysis was based on unadjusted estimates, additional variables like smoking cigarette, obesity, and extra lifestyles variables could regarded confounding variables. Furthermore, our study comprised research with limited data, single-center studies with clinical heterogeneity, & varying patient histories, might led to reduced statistical power & variable outcomes between the studies. To further validate the effects of letrozole with menopausal gonadotropin in stimulation of ovary in patients with PCOS, large enough sample size clinical studies should be conducted.

5. Conclusion

Finally, this review contains only RCTs and provides a complete evaluation of the extent of letrozole with menopausal gonadotropin in ovulation induction in patients with polycystic ovarian syndrome. It was shown that combining LE with an intramuscular injection of HMG had good therapeutic benefits on ovulation induction, a shorter treatment cycle, and a significant diagnostic pregnancy rate, making it a potential treatment option for PCOS infertile patients. More research is needed to confirm the benefits of letrozole coupled with menopausal gonadotropin on ovarian stimulation in polycystic ovarian syndrome patients. Given restricted number of investigations reviewed, clinical trials in bigger scale were needed in order to confirm the enduring letrozole benefits coupled with menopausal gonadotropin in induction of ovulation in PCOS patients.

6. Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts of interest to declare for any of the authors.

7. Acknowledgement

Not applicable.

Figure legends

Figure 1. The process of Literature Search - Flow diagram.

Figure 2. The risk of bias in the meta-randomized analysis's trials.

Figure 3. Ovarian follicleson patients with polycystic ovary syndrome (fixed-effects model).

Figure 4. Subgroup of therapy months on patients with polycystic ovary syndrome.

Figure 5. The funnel plots for Ovarian follicles.

Table legends

Table 1. Characteristics of the 5 studies in the meta-analysis.

Author		Age	Size	Types of studies	Doses	Therapy
Year	Country	(EG VS CG)	EG /CG	and intervention		(weeks)
		Mean±SD				
Hao	China	25.3±2.8vs.	100/90	RCT comparing the use of letrozole	letrozole 2.5-5.0 mg/d+ human	6
2019		26.3±2.1		combined human menopausal gonadotropin	menopausal gonadotropin 75U/d	
[19]						
Li	China	30.29±0.31vs.	46/46	RCT comparing the use of letrozole	letrozole 2.5 mg/d+human	24
2021		31.18±0.29		combined human menopausal gonadotropin	menopausal gonadotropin 75U/d	
[20]						
Shi	China	26.1±3.2vs.	48/48	RCT comparing the use of letrozole	letrozole 5 mg/d+human	24
2019		26.3±3.0		combined human menopausal	menopausal gonadotropin 75U/d	

[21]				gonadotropin			
Chen	China	26.4±4.2vs.	52/52	RCT comparing the use of letrozole	letrozole 2.5-5.0 mg/d+ human		8
2016		27.7±5.2		combined human menopausal gonadotropin	menopausal gonadotropin 75U/d		
[22]							
Giuseppe	Italy	34.5±1.6vs.	80/45	RCT comparing the use of letrozole	letrozole 2.5 mg/d+human		6
2018		34±2.1		combined human menopausal gonadotropin	menopausal gonadotropin 75U/d		
[23]							

Table 2. Characteristics of the 5 included studies on Ovarian follicles.

Author	Country	Intervention	Ovarian follicles	Therapy	Blinding
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		Age			Pre-T	Post-T	months	
Hao	estern	≥18	EG:sletrozole	2.5-5.0 mg/d+	1.22±2.07	5.27±2.41	<6	Double-blind
2019			human	menopausal				
[19]			gonadotropin	75U/d	1.94±1.73	3.64±2.73		
			CG:human	menopausal				
			gonadotropin	75U/d				
Li	estern	≥18	EG:etrozole	2.5 mg/d+human	2.37±2.17	4.47±3.47	≥6	Double-blind
2021			menopausal	gonadotropin				
[20]			75U/d		1.14±0.73	2.64±1.73		
			CG:human	menopausal				
			gonadotropin	75U/d				
Shi	estern	≥18	EG:letrozole	5 mg/d+human	1.37±2.17	5.37±2.47	≥6	Double-blind
2019			menopausal	gonadotropin				
			75U/d					

[21]			CG:human	menopausal	0.14±1.73	3.24±2.73		
			gonadotropin 75U/d					
Chen	estern	≥18	EG:letrozole	2.5-5.0 mg/d+	2.15±1.79	4.78±8.70	<6	Double-blind
2016			human	menopausal				
			gonadotropin 75U/d					
[22]					2.21±1.54	2.98±5.39		
			CG:human	menopausal				
			gonadotropin 75U/d					
Giuseppe	western	≥18	EG:letrozole	2.5	2.7±1.40	5.3±3.70	<6	Double-blind
2018			mg/d+human	menopausal				
			gonadotropin 75U/d					
[23]					2.6±1.70	2.1±4.1		
			CG:human	menopausal				
			gonadotropin 75U/d					

EG, letrozole combined human menopausal gonadotropin group; CG, control group.
